

686 Definitions of 'Identity'

1. A belief, which is expressed through a series of theological propositions.
2. a box of tools and signs.
3. a certain 'kind of person' or even as several different 'kinds' at once ... at a given time and place.
4. a certain "kind of person" in a given context.
5. a changing discursive phenomenon constantly shaped by an individual's interpersonal relations, society and culture emerging in interaction and communication.
6. a claim made about the collective personality of a country's people.
7. A close affinity of a group of people based on assigned similarities.
8. a close similarity or affinity.
9. a cognitive construct, organized sets of self-perceptions and attached feelings that an individual holds about self with regard to some social category.
10. a coherent conceptualization of values, beliefs, and future goals to which the individual is firmly committed.
11. a coherent sense of self that depends upon the awareness that one's endeavors and one's life make sense.
12. a coincidence of placements and announcements.
13. a collection of attributes.
14. a collection of reifying, significant, and endorsable narratives about a person.
15. a collection of stories about a person that are reifying and endorsable.
16. a collection of stories about individuals which are reifying, endorsable and significant.
17. a collective identity that is based on the common system of political values.
18. a collective legacy, not individual choice.
19. a combination of a finite number of attributes that the IoT device has.
20. a combination of organization's character, "what we indubitably are" and culture, "what we feel we are".
21. a combination of the role that an agent plays in its interactions with other agents and the package of rules that is needed to establish and maintain that role.
22. a communicative construct by means of which the members of a strategic group distinguish themselves from other groups or from different social strata.
23. a complex dynamic that emerges and is transformed through intra-personal and inter-personal processes that are socio-politically and historically embedded.
24. a complex fusion of the inner self and the outer social context.
25. a complex integrative psychological mechanism which affects the personal and professional development of a human.
26. a comprehensive theoretical concept with three components: a cognitive component-self-concept; an emotional component - self-esteem; and an action-oriented component - expectancy for control.
27. a concept covering not only the picture that an organisation has of itself but also the way in which the organisation manifests itself.
28. a concept encompassing an individual's personal worldview and beliefs -their selfhood or subjectivity.
29. a concept that can be examined through multiple levels of analysis (personal, cultural, social).
30. a concept, including brand uniqueness, meaning, purpose, values and individuality.

31. a condition or fact that a person or thing is itself and not something else.
32. a configuration of constitutional givens, idiosyncratic libidinal needs, favoured capacities, significant identifications, effective defences, successful sublimations, and consistent roles.
33. a conscious belonging to a certain category of people, which becomes changeable and uncertain, "fluid" in an era of social change.
34. a conscious sense of individual identity,... an unconscious striving for a continuity of personal character.
35. a conscious sense of individual uniqueness.
36. a constantly evolving state of being, composed of multiple, interacting, socially acquired and internally inherited characteristics.
37. a continual work in progress , constructed and altered by the totality of life experience.
38. a continuous dynamic process of interpretation and reinterpretation of experiences, as an answer to the questions, 'who am I at this moment?'
39. a continuous process where the sense of belongingness to a community interacts with the desire to be a unique individual.
40. a continuum of a person's self-conviction.
41. a cultural construct in the area of cultural studies.
42. a demarcation both from the very rich as well as from the poor.
43. a dimension of human interaction.
44. a dynamic process of construction and reproduction over time, in direct relation or opposition to specific other groups and interests.
45. a dynamic process of socially negotiating and internationally constructing certain roles, as relevant within the particular context of a particular interaction.
46. a dynamic system used to organize the individual's internal states as well as the boundaries between self and other.
47. a dynamic view of self, negotiated in a specific social context and informed by past history, events, personal narratives, routines, and ways of participating.
48. a dynamic, processual, multilayered phenomenon that positions an individual, and defines his or her "being" in the world.
49. a feeling of singleness and continuity in conception of self.
50. a feeling of uniqueness combined with a feeling of connectedness to a greater whole.
51. a fluid relationship with oneself and with others.
52. a frame of reference within which the social and political situations are recognized.
53. a function of both external (social) and internal (agentic) experiences.
54. a goal that allows for different forms of goal pursuit.
55. a group's process of inclusion and exclusion, a constant renegotiation that can include racial ancestry but is not exclusively linked to it.
56. a higher order organizational aggregate that gives organizational stakeholders a sense of belonging and identification.
57. a horizon of meaning from which we know the world.
58. a kind of confirmation and realization of the subject compared with the object or the otherness from the perspective of philosophy.
59. a label or concept that distinguishes one individual from another - in essence, it refers to 'who you are'.
60. a layering of events of participation and reification by which our experience and its social interpretation inform each other.

61. a lesbian's woman identified feelings and ideas.
62. a life story which individuals begin construing, consciously or unconsciously, in late adolescence.
63. a life story, an internalized narrative integration of past, present and anticipated future which provides lives with a sense of unity and purpose.
64. a living asset, such that a device is given its identity at birth (eg manufacturing).
65. a manner cate themselves psychologically in relation systems, and the way they perceive the in relation to those systems.
66. a matter of the way we portray ourselves, and also how others interpret our portrayal and portray us back.
67. a means by which individuals understand who they are, and their fundamental characteristics as human beings.
68. a mechanism to actualise a shared set of local rules.
69. A membership of a particular race.
70. a mental representation of a person as perceived by the person or by others.
71. a metaphor for self - in context and states that music can be used and experienced in a way which positions people in relation to time and place, other persons or transcendental values.
72. a modern social phenomena referring to labelling.
73. a name or persona.
74. a narrative of the self, which is constructed through reflection and introspection, and has to be performed.
75. a narrative representation of self that aims to be morally intelligible.
76. a negotiated experience within a community, where "we define who we are by the ways we experience ourselves through participation".
77. a negotiation between how one sees oneself and how one is seen by others.
78. a negotiation between the self, other people and the context in which people live and work.
79. a network of feelings of belonging and exclusion from human groups.
80. a part of an individual's self-concept, which arises from the awareness of one's membership in a group (or groups).
81. a part of the individual's self-construct which is based on two dimensions — construct of ethnic ancestry and future aspirations.
82. a part of the self composed of the meanings that a person attaches to a particular role he or she typically plays in society.
83. a particularity and that being-perceived which exists fundamentally through other people.
84. a people's source of meaning and experience in the process of self-construction.
85. a perceived similarity bound by a narrative pegged onto a "thing-event".
86. a performative act, realized when people expose who they are at each moment in specific social interactions.
87. a person's internal and evolving sense of self (both as an individual and as a member of various social groups).
88. a person's self image.
89. a person's self-concept, or how someone thinks about and views themselves both socially and physically.
90. a person's self-image both as an individual and as part of a group.
91. a person's sense of who they are and how they relate to the social world.

92. a person's understanding of who they are.
93. a personal conception of his/herself as male or female (or both at the same time) as well as the way we express our gender roles in dressing, behavior and personal appearance.
94. a personal conception of oneself as male or female (or rarely, both, or neither).
95. a personal sense of uniqueness based on an inner set of values.
96. A person's cognitive schema around a set of moral traits.
97. a person's essential continuous self.
98. a person's self-understanding of their gender.
99. a person's sense of her meaning in the world and her relation to other people and groups, as well as others' perceptions of those.
100. a person's sense of who they are, both on a personal level and in relation to their experiences with others in their environment and society.
101. a person's name and other facts about who they are.
102. a phenomenon which is flexible with regard to its features and its scope, and which is constructed by interlocutors in communicative processes, i.e., in sign-based interaction.
103. a prerequisite for appropriate social adaptation and psychosocial efficacy.
104. a procedure of identification and not as a process of discovery or awakening.
105. a process and not a found object.
106. a process located in the core of the individual and yet also in the core of his or her communal culture.
107. a process of actively creating that with which one wishes to identify something she regards as being ambiguous or obscure, involving multiple potentialities.
108. a process of internal and external adjustment.
109. a process of self-reflection in which individuals consider their abilities and potential and become aware of who they are.
110. a process that is always undergoing transformation.
111. a process that is both inherently personal as well as social.
112. a process that occurs due to the engagement with social phenomenon at a given time and in a given space.
113. A process, a matter of 'becoming' rather than being.
114. a process, one strung out between subject and object.
115. a product of active environmental selfregulation influenced by the functional principles of self as described in the models of Epstein.
116. a product of situated social action and a cultural effect.
117. a production that shows the past and present but is incapable of revealing the future.
118. a range of beliefs and attitudes about the professions for which an individual is preparing themselves.
119. A reflected image within marketing function norms.
120. a reflexive construct or experiential modality through which one knows oneself and claims recognition.
121. A reflexive perception that how people understand themselves is shaped by social contact.
122. a reflexively organised endeavour or a project orchestrated primarily by the individual and individual choices.
123. a relational phenomenon.

124. a relationship between one entity and a particular registration.
125. a relationship between self and others— [which] may hence be applied to any entity, individual or collective.
126. a relationship, not a possession.
127. a response to what and who the individual is and to society, which has faced great challenges in recent years due to the formation of virtual space.
128. a result of the individualization of a person due to his/her isolation from the forces of nature and other people.
129. a self-conception organized around a set of moral traits and as one of many possible identities that people use as a basis for self-definition.
130. a self-perception about the profession based on attitudes, beliefs, feelings, values, motivations, and experiences.
131. a self-referential description that provides contextually appropriate answers to the question "Who am I?".
132. a self-understanding to which one is emotionally attached and that informs one's behaviour and interpretations.
133. a sense of being or feeling American and is empirically unrelated to self-described liberalism or conservatism.
134. a sense of belonging to a community with which one shares ideals and values.
135. a sense of belonging to a country whose citizens share a common language, land, cultural heritage, customs, emotions, memories, political system, beliefs, symbols, national heroes, history, economics, art and literature, and even religion.
136. a sense of connection to the values and emphases of counselling psychology.
137. a sense of continuity that gives adolescents a link to their past and a direction for their future.
138. a sense of sameness, a unity of personality now felt by the individual and recognized by others as having consistency in time - of being, as it were, an irreversible historical fact.
139. a sense of self in contrast to the other.
140. a sense of self in relation to others.
141. a sense of self that encompasses who people think they are, and how other people regard them.
142. a sense of self.
143. a sense of self-sameness, authenticity, wholeness, and belonging to the world and other individuals.
144. a sense of teacher self that results from a productive combination of key personal and professional subjectivities or beliefs.
145. a set of "meanings" applied to self in a social role or situation, defining what it means to be who one is.
146. a set of aesthetic characteristics and values that are expressed by a building and reflect its identity or that which distinguishes it.
147. a set of attributes relating to an entity.
148. a set of attributes that uniquely identifies the user within a domain.
149. a set of behaviors that others interpret as representing certain beliefs or systems.
150. a set of beliefs and values that a person has.
151. a set of beliefs concerning who one is in relation to one's personal attributes, relationships, and group affiliations.

152. a set of characteristics that allows a subject, an object or an event to be “different” and “equivalent” in relation to another subject, object or event.
153. a set of circumstances which make a person that specific person.
154. a set of culturally and historically formed statuses that are conditioned and internalized through the institutions most directly linked to them.
155. a set of data by which a person is identified.
156. a set of practices rather than ascriptive features.
157. a set of putative facts about a person that ground that person’s pleasant or unpleasant emotions about himself.
158. a set of reifying, significant, endorsable stories about a person.
159. a set of self-referential descriptive traits, personal characteristics, life goals, and values that are meaningful to an individual.
160. a set of social and human components that indicate the individuals within their community and give them the status of distinguishing them from others.
161. a set of socio-cultural, psychological, and personal characteristics by which an individual is considered part of a group.
162. a set of statements that organization members perceive to be central, distinctive, and enduring to their organization.
163. a set of unique features that ensure its continuous recognizability and distinguish it from any other city.
164. a shared value that is discovered and formulated together.
165. a shorthand label for varying construction of nation-and state-hood.
166. a significant, endorsable, and reified narrative about a person.
167. a social category, a set of persons marked by a label and distinguished by rules deciding membership and (alleged) characteristic features or attributes.
168. a social concept that affects collective action and outcomes, even though activists’ identities are constantly being changed and often tap into other preexisting sources of identification.
169. a social construct and the combination of multiple identities.
170. a social construct that is maintained, modified, and even reshaped by social relationships.
171. a social construct, which is ideological, perceptual, and habitual.
172. a social process, a complex, dynamic, unique, individual as well as collective, projects that depend on the context.
173. a socially consequential, social category.
174. a socially constructed representation of an individual’s self - perception of his/her own interactions within the employment environment.
175. a sociocultural construction occurring within a particular social context.
176. a sociocultural rather than a psychological construct.
177. a socio-cultural representation.
178. a solidarity with group ideals.
179. a spatiotemporal sense of sameness.
180. a special case of knowledge problem.
181. a species.
182. a specific city’s self-consciousness developed through history and in relation with other cities.

183. a stance taken by a person to form a tangible framework as a means to define who he or she is.
184. a state similar to the sublime, where differences fall away and one's self essentially melts into and becomes part of "the other".
185. a strong emotional and psychological connection between the team and the fan.
186. a strong separation between 'we' and 'they'."
187. a structure which allows the mobilization of resources, and which is used for orientation in everyday life.
188. a style of the image and shape as each person.
189. a subject (human) that is authenticated in various ways.
190. a subject expert, whose main responsibility is to transfer subject knowledge to the students.
191. a subjective sense of an invigorating sameness and continuity.
192. a subtype of meaning and holds that entities with an identity are entities that have an understanding of their own meaning in a given practice.
193. a symbolic identification- differentiation building process based on a referential frame (territory, class, ethnicity, culture, gender, age).
194. a symbolic project.
195. a system that involves core identities, short-term identities, and situational identities.
196. A systematic contrast with other identities.
197. a territory where we can clearly distinguish a layering of that territory based on different identities.
198. a theory (or schema) of an individual that describes, interrelates and explains his or her relevant features, characteristics and experiences.
199. a theory of self that is formed and maintained through actual or imagined interpersonal agreement about what the self is like.
200. a time-based work in progress.
201. a total integration, the integration, that is, of the elements of collective identity and the dynamisms of personality.
202. a type of personhood and view that it is always performed and negotiated by individuals in their social lives.
203. a unique combination of facial geometry, texture (albedo and displacement), eye color and hair style.
204. a user's real name/credentials or as a persistent online pseudonym.
205. a validated self-understanding that places and defines the individual; it establishes what and where an actor is socially.
206. a very private experience of the self in relation to others.
207. a visual image of the environment that reflects special or unique qualities.
208. a way in which we differ from others in various areas of our lives.
209. a way of describing a sense of self that is in practice.
210. a way of placing oneself and others at a particular position in society.
211. a way to express identity through the physical environment.
212. a concept for urban branding or urban industry, with a great emphasis on image of a place.
213. a contextual,dynamic identity in communication by reviewing identity in other fields.

214. ability and will to live in and to develop the territory including both local and regional levels of "minor homeland".
215. acting to fulfil the expectations of the role , coordinating and negotiating interaction with the role partners and manipulating the environment to control the resources for which the role has a responsibility.
216. an abiding sense of selfhood that is the core of what makes life predictable to an individual.
217. an action, a variable process of identification, rather than as a fixed, singular or 'immanent' feature of the self.
218. an affiliation that develops over time; that is, it is a resource for communicating aspects of positions and affiliations that develop as artifacts of local interaction.
219. an aggregate of the selves associated with one individual person and tends to use the terms self and identity interchangeably.
220. an ambivalence that is in close relation with temporality.
221. an aspect of self-concept including specific attributes of the individual such as competence, talent, and sociality.
222. an assuredness of one's self and one's capabilities.
223. an attained but forever-to-be-revised sense of the reality of the self within social reality.
224. an attribute of a thing, which is shared with something else (ie, 'similarity'); on the second, identity is seem as a unique attribute of a thing (ie, 'dissimilarity').
225. an awareness of a demarcation between the body image and that of the mother's.
226. an awareness of personal selfsameness and continuity of one's existence in time and space and the perception of the fact that others recognize one's sameness and continuity.
227. an awareness of self, national identity would appear to imply the awareness of self within a defined national context.
228. an emotional, strong affiliation with a permanent group.
229. an enduring, fundamental aspect of one's self with a sense of membership in an ethnic group, with attitudes and feelings associated with that membership.
230. an error such that an individual is punished for someone else's crime; and for the same crime, the criminal is falsely acquitted.
231. an ever-incomplete psychic construction that consists of reflective processes of comparison.
232. an ever-shifting performance of the self, created for the self and others, and made meaningful based upon the sociocultural context in which it is performed and interpreted.
233. an evolving nexus of where we have been and who we are becoming.
234. an evolving nexus where all the forces that constitute [one's] life converge in the mystery of self.
235. an evolving nexus where all the forces that constitute my life converge in the mystery of self.
236. an existence that is recognized as a certain character inside specific circumstances, which enables it to shift depending on situations.
237. an extreme case of similarity.
238. an habitual association of ideas.

239. an imagining of self.
240. an immediate simple self-identity.
241. an important structure of self-consciousness, which determines socially-meaningful forms of behavior and has an impact on relations between people, starting from interpersonal and finishing with inter-state.
242. an individual's awareness of his or her membership in a generational group and the significance of this group to the individual.
243. an individual's mentally accessible, important and essential characteristics of self.
244. an individual's or group's sense of self.
245. an individual's answer to the question, 'Who am I?'
246. an individual's conception of the nature of the self.
247. an individual's self-conceptualization that places the individual either within or in opposition to a social grouping.
248. an individual's self-image and sense of belonging to certain social categories.
249. an individual's sense of belonging to a specific cultural or ethnic group.
250. an inner sense of sameness and continuity, which is matched by the mirroring eyes of at least one significant other.
251. an instance of the human mental construction.
252. an integrated, coherent, and goal-directed self... which is critical to well-being and psychological adjustment.
253. an integrative configuration of the self in the world.
254. an intentional accumulation of suitable personal information that together distinguish one entity from another.
255. an internal process by which individuals define their sense of self.
256. an internal, self-constructed, dynamic organization of drives, abilities, beliefs, and individual history.
257. an internalized and evolving life story.
258. an internalized set of behavioral expectations associated with a particular role.
259. an internally consistent sense of self.
260. an interpretive framework and a set of interpretive practices, a particular way of making sense of social conduct and expressive culture.
261. an intersubjectively achieved social and cultural phenomenon.
262. an intuitive understanding of the self, including the way an individual relates to or differentiates himself or herself from the group(s).
263. an observable social psychological process, transactive in nature.
264. an organized set of perceptions that an individual has about the meaning of his sexual attractions and desires, directed toward forming a sense of self within existing social categories.
265. an oscillating, relatively sustainable aggregate of relations, which is both sameness and promoting distinction.
266. an unconscious striving for continuity of experience.
267. an unfixable and ever-changing "being-in-the-world" which would be rendered lifeless by the confinement of rules.
268. any category label or positionality to which a person self-associates either by choice or by endowment, due to identification with that label or because the performance of it will lead to some desired end.

269. any category label to which a consumer self-associates, either by choice or endowment.
270. any social category in which an individual is eligible to be a member.
271. asking questions of self-reflection (Who do we think we are? Who do we think we should be?).
272. aspects of one's cultural heritage, such as "language, ethnic, and national affiliations that are part of one's history".
273. attention to individual character of every environment and restraint from uniformity and similarity of urban environments.
274. awareness of multiple levels of being.
275. bearing upon the four different pillars of "personality, self-concept, identity project, and self-presentation".
276. becoming aware of oneself as a person, expressing one's uniqueness, and expressing one's commonalities.
277. behavioral responses such as lifestyle, beliefs, and customs, acquired from and accepted by a community.
278. being a certain 'kind of person,' a concept that can be applied to nearly any aspect of a person's life.
279. being a member of a category.
280. being about the recognition of persons who differ in gender, skin, colour or culture.
281. being at one with oneself whilst simultaneously feeling a sense of affinity and belonging with a community.
282. being composed of a genetic inheritance together with a particular way of organising experience that is in turn structured by a given cultural context.
283. being different from others.
284. being made of two parts, the body process and product.
285. being social by definition, because identifying always involves interaction.
286. belonging to a group or an interest, which distinguishes one or out of which one or a group is known.
287. belonging together, but then reasons that the phrase's meaning depends on which word is given sway.
288. both a shared definition and a process.
289. both the identity certificate and the information that can uniquely identify the owner.
290. categories people use to specify who they are and to locate themselves relative to other people.
291. certain information that can represent a real world entity on the Internet.
292. character portrayal involving two or more otherwise objectively distinct literature characters who have supernatural bonds of identity.
293. characteristics, beliefs and behaviors that make up a person's self-image.
294. collections of stories about persons.
295. common language, territory and history.
296. complex, culturally and historically determined, continuous process of finding the person's identity with himself.
297. concerned with the binding together of people, either by individual self-affiliation or as a result of categorization by others, as members of a particular group.

298. consisting of three dialectically related aspects: social identity, personal identity and self-identity.
299. construction of differentiation/identification between 'us' and 'them'.
300. construction of meaning on the basis of a cultural attribute, or related set of cultural attributes, that is/are given priority over other sources of meaning.
301. content and illumination as style to show the application of linear models to illumination-robust face recognition problem.
302. conveyed internally within firms and socially constructed by individuals.
303. created and not from a single source.
304. customary practice and of beliefs, values, sanctions, rules, motives and satisfactions associated with it.
305. dependent upon (structural) relations that fundamental objects create.
306. dialogue with or in struggle against others.
307. difference, and difference is defined by boundaries.
308. dynamic and continuously transforming under social contexts that regularly affect BIPOC.
309. efforts to retain a sense of security as one becomes increasingly autonomous.
310. ego-structure: an internal, self-constructed, dynamic organisation.
311. encompassing multiple intersecting social categories either imposed by oneself or others that define those that arise out of different historical, political, cultural and social phenomena over time.
312. encompassing the "Soul", "Mind" and "Voice" of an organization.
313. essentially bound self or as socially constructed entity.
314. establishing the what and where a person is in social terms and notes that identification entails two processes which he labeled identification of and identification with.
315. everything that the stories of my experiences are comprised of, the emotional value I place on those experiences, all my beliefs about everything I experience, and everything I call and believe to be "me."
316. feeling of belonging to groups in Facebook by joining to these groups, sharing and collaborating with others in groups.
317. flexible, fluid, and multi-aspected and as co-constructed in ongoing interactions in relation to specific contexts.
318. having a clearly delineated self-definition comprised of those goals, values and beliefs to which the person is unequivocally committed.
319. having different dimensions, where each dimension has a given set of discrete characteristics.
320. high-order structures that organize autobiographical memories on the basis of personality and role-based themes of one's self-concept.
321. how a person sees themselves and is seen by others.
322. how a person sees themselves based on values, motives, experiences and beliefs related to their profession.
323. how a person thinks of and defines himself, taking into consideration his own expectations of himself and the roles society assumes he will carry out.
324. how a person understands his or her relationship to the world, how the relationship is constructed across time and space, and how the person understands possibilities for the future.

325. how an individual defines oneself as a "kind of person".
326. how an individual thinks about herself.
327. how an individual thinks about, understands, and judges her/himself as a social being.
328. how learning changes who we are and creates personal histories of becoming in the context of our communities.
329. how people define themselves.
330. how people understand their relationship to the world, how that relationship is constructed across time and space, and how people understand their possibilities for the future.
331. how the organization wants to be perceived and strategy as instrumental purpose, that is, what needs to be done to achieve performance goals.
332. how the self conceives of itself, and labels itself.
333. how we see ourselves.
334. how you identify with a group.
335. how you identify with a particular social role.
336. how you identify with your personal characteristics.
337. identification with both one's ethnocultural minority in-group and one's society of residence.
338. incorporating a woman's choices for herself, her priorities, and the guiding principles by which she makes decisions.
339. individuals' perceptions of who they are and how others perceive them.
340. individuals' perception of their characteristics, abilities, beliefs and values integrated with perceptions of future development.
341. information.
342. integrity with multilevel borders.
343. involving a process of self-construction and individuation.
344. knowing who and what you are regardless of where you are.
345. knowing who God is, knowing what He has already done, and knowing who He made you to be.
346. knowledge of one's membership of a given social category, along with the importance ascribed to such membership.
347. language, art, and thought of any phenomenon, and the relations between these components in an environment.
348. life-story construction.
349. maintaining a social group despite changes in membership and practice over time.
350. making distinctions between what is inside and what is outside.
351. meaning-making.
352. multidimensional, including aspects of race, class, gender, nationality, education, profession, beliefs, etc.
353. multifaceted and dynamic, a collection of versions of self-created as people position themselves and are positioned in relation to varied social practices.
354. multiple presentations of self which are (re)constructed in and through social interaction across social contexts and demonstrated through actions and emotions.
355. multiple, a site of struggle, and continually changing over time and space.

356. multiple, changing across time and space, and a site of struggle between competing ideologies and desire.
357. narrative.
358. not being a "regular Chinese kid."
359. not being like a woman.
360. one aspect of the broader concept of self.
361. one component of an individual's overall self concept.
362. one or more pieces of information that may cause others to believe they know who someone is.
363. one upheld by groups opposing dominant institutions, and project identity as one aimed at building a new identity and changing society.
364. one's professional self-concept based on attributes, beliefs, values, motives, and experiences.
365. one's sense of belonging to a social category, along with a view about how people who belong to the category should behave.
366. one's sense of who one is.
367. one's understanding of self, including one's skills, values, social positioning, purpose in life, and impact on others.
368. one's capacity to answer for oneself within the discursive space of questions.
369. one's knowledge of membership in certain social groups and the social meanings attached to these groups.
370. one's social role and commitment to working.
371. ones socially constructed meanings of and commitment to a collective social group(s) who share a set of learned values, beliefs and behaviors.
372. ones' sense of purpose, value and belonging in the workplace.
373. our digital footprint is being constructed by the social interactions we are developing via our internet connected/mobile devices.
374. our own understanding of who we are, who other people think we are, and our understanding of how we relate socially to others.
375. our understanding of who we are and who other people are, and reciprocally, other people's understanding of themselves and of others (which includes us).
376. part of a relationship involving two or more entities designed to express equality, unity and uniformity, as opposed to whatever is not the same.
377. particular form of social representation that represents the relationship between the individual and others.
378. people's sense of who they are as its main concern is to answer the simple question of who we are.
379. people's concepts of who they are, of what sort of people they are, and how they relate to others.
380. perceiving oneself as a member of a larger group and having the consciousness of this group within the context of (or in opposition to) larger groups.
381. perception of belonging to their employing organization's in-group.
382. political and/or cultural associations and is therefore understood as a subset of genos.
383. position in society.
384. proclamation of difference emerging from the correspondence between social and mental structures.

385. produced between people and within social relations.
386. psychological formations ... complexes of memories, sentiments, knowledge and ideas.
387. recognition as a certain kind of person.
388. recognized similarity bound by a narrative pegged onto something.
389. referring to social categories defined by membership rules and characteristic attributes, including ascriptive traits.
390. reflected (processed) memories.
391. reflective determination, as a result of the self-referential movement of negativity.
392. reflexive self-relation, but distinguishes between two notions, formal and concrete.
393. relationally constructed allowing for multiple, fluid or shifting belonging to various categories.
394. role-playing.
395. roles individuals occupy, specific characteristics, and group membership.
396. rooted in kinship and cultural forms of address in specific social settings.
397. a kind of feeling and emotional belonging to a society that causes national unity and cohesion and has different material, cultural and psychological dimensions that cause societies to differ from each other
398. sameness in all that constitutes the objective reality of a thing.
399. sameness of a thing with itself, through comparing this thing with itself over time (in different places), in contrast with the notion of diversity.
400. sameness of all properties.
401. sameness of essential or generic character in different instances.
402. sameness.
403. selected or inherited traits that define people or communities as certain kinds of individuals or groups.
404. self- conception - one's theory of oneself.
405. self-belief of the characteristics that the entity has.
406. self-definition of a unique individual in terms of interpersonal or intra-group differentiations.
407. sense of group identity based on one's perception that he/she shares with a particular racial group.
408. sense of self, of its person, of being who he is. It is the mental representation of a person about himself/herself.
409. sets of social expectations related to ourselves and others that are grounded in the interplay between similarities and differences.
410. social and cultural conception of an individual as a male or a female.
411. socially constructed images of self and other that we display to and negotiate with others.
412. societal assignments of who we are, and subjectivity as who we believe we are.
413. society's understanding of themselves and of what they represent in the world.
414. Sofia's experiences of being, becoming and belonging as they relate to the profession.
415. someone who belongs to more than one religion or faith group.
416. someone's conceptions of what a particular person or group is actually like.

417. something that is constructed, as something that involves a period of exploration, reflection, and commitment.
418. something that is made, unmade and remade in the contexts of dynamic social, political, economic and historical processes in which there are stable and consistent components as well.
419. stories about a person's practices and belongingness to particular groups based on ritualized forms of practice, all expressed in discourse.
420. stories about people.
421. stories about persons.
422. stories claimed by the individual and conferred by the group answering the questions "Who am I?" and "What makes me, me?".
423. strong indistinguishability.
424. telling one's autobiography.
425. terms that seem inevitably to spin in elliptical orbits around any attempt to conceptualize human beings.
426. that aspect of a person's self- conceptualization which results from identification with a broader group in opposition to others on the basis of perceived cultural differentiation and/or common descent.
427. that particular set of traits, beliefs, and allegiances that, in short- or long-term ways, gives one consistent personality and mode of social being,
428. that relation that everything bears to itself and to no other thing.
429. that which identifies a person and distinguishes one person from another.
430. the ability to continue to experience oneself as being the same throughout the successive transformations which form the basis of a person's emotional experience.
431. the ability to substantialise career goals and results from the social learning process achieved through interactions with others.
432. the absence of difference (i.e. mutual absence) , delimited by differenceness.
433. the academic metaphor for self, in context.
434. the accrued confidence that one's ability to maintain inner sameness and continuity (one's ego in the psychological sense) is matched by the sameness and continuity of one's meaning for others.
435. the accumulation of individual and large-group historical memory.
436. the adolescent's search for who he is, what he believes in and values, and what he wants to accomplish and get out of life.
437. the affiliation each thing carries only to itself.
438. the affiliations and values either claimed or ascribed to an individual and the actions or behaviours of the individual in diverse contexts.
439. the answer not only to the subjective question "who am I?" but also to the collective question "who am I like?"
440. the answer people give to the question of "who we are",
441. the answer to the self-referential question, "Who am I?" ("Who are we") by an entity.
442. the assignation of an agent to an action.
443. the attitudes, values, knowledge, beliefs and skills shared with others within a professional group.
444. the awareness of a sense of being "not a sense of who I am but that I am."

445. the awareness of belonging to a community of citizens, which has a value meaning.
446. the awareness of the fact that there is a self-sameness and continuity.
447. the basis of other elements.
448. the becoming and being of an academic scholar, with writing skills as a means of acquiring and performing the status and skills of a scholar.
449. the biological continuity of a single human organism.
450. the capacity of an individual to recognize themselves.
451. the capacity to keep feeling like oneself amid the succession of transformations that are the basis of a person's emotional experience.
452. the capacity to see oneself as having continuity and sameness and to act accordingly.
453. the central, distinctive, and enduring qualities of an organization.
454. the characteristics determining who or what a person or thing is.
455. the characteristics that establish who a person is and where he or she is going.
456. the characteristics they have that distinguish them from others.
457. the coherence of lines of action perceived by the individual.
458. the collective production of public discourses by the institutions of journalists: professional associations, unions, or press councils.
459. the combination of self-categorization and its evaluation.
460. the commitments and identifications which provide the frame or horizon within which I can try to determine from case to case what is good, or valuable, or what ought to be done, or what I endorse or oppose.
461. the complete perception an individual has of themselves, including how they differentiate themselves from others.
462. the complex set of assertions which make up the actor's concept of self.
463. the complex, enduring process of situating and understanding self, and how this relates to the communities that individuals interact with(in).
464. the composite of answers that an actor constructs to the "Who am I" questions.
465. the concept of making use of mobile communication in the establishment, development and protection of citizen identity.
466. the concepts of self that individuals hold about themselves.
467. the condition of being oneself or itself, and not another.
468. the condition of being simultaneously both "one's self or itself and not another."
469. the condition of being the same with something described or asserted.
470. the condition of socially being one thing and not another.
471. the configuration of the defining characteristics of a person.
472. the confluence of the person's self-chosen or ascribed commitments, personal characteristics and beliefs about herself.
473. the connectedness and continuity of a person's experience, united by causality; the existence of a person comprises merely these causal experiences, along with his or her brain and body.
474. the constant shifts in positioning by individuals as a response to their individual characteristics, their socially constructed personas, and the different subject positions that their social contexts place them.
475. the constellation of elements (eg, group memberships, personality traits) that make each individual unique and distinctive.

476. the core quality facilitating an adult commitment to work and love.
477. the culmination, in some unique way, of all the childhood identifications in concordance with the rules offered by society.
478. the degree to which an individual view an IT use as integral to his or her sense of self.
479. the degree to which one is loved and feels loved.
480. the different ways in which people are perceived as a certain type of person in the context in which they find themselves.
481. the digital representation of the information known about a specific individual or organization.
482. the distinct personality of an individual regarded as a persisting entity.
483. the distinguishing character or personality of an individual.
484. the dynamic process through which individuals comes to understand themselves and others.
485. the emotional attachment of employees to a company.
486. the enduring, sincere, and significant first-person accounts of who we are, that we tell ourselves and to others.
487. the extent to which a person considers moral concerns to be ... moral.
488. the extent to which a worker perceives his or her work as a professional one, and the value the worker attaches to the work.
489. the extent to which a worker views use of ESM as integral to his or her sense of self.
490. the fact of being who or what a person or thing is.
491. the facts making the defendant a proper party.
492. the features that make the difference for living things or objects.
493. the feeling of belonging to a residential neighborhood.
494. the general sense of who we are as individuals.
495. the generic set and operationalized function of the rules a carrier has originated, adopted and retained.
496. the genes it expresses and those it represses.
497. the given narrative in which a community of communication recognizes itself.
498. the grouping of individual characteristics that makes a person or thing unique.
499. the history of a relationship between two entities.
500. the human capacity – rooted in language – to know 'who's who' (and hence 'what's what').
501. the idea one has about oneself, one's characteristic properties, one's own body, and the values one considers important.
502. the identification of an individual with a group united by political values, historical narratives, preferences in behavior models.
503. the identifying property of a single-person.
504. the identity and feeling of belonging to a group.
505. the images of individuality and distinctiveness ('selfhood') held and projected by an actor and formed (and modified over time) through relations with significant others.
506. the images of what the library is, what it is aiming to be in the future, what it should do and how.
507. the imaginings of self in worlds of action.

508. the importance attributed to athletic role preserved by the individual as well as being strength and a privilege.
509. the individual possessing a clear and stable understanding of his or her career goals, interests, personality, and talents.
510. the individual property or as something that emerges through social interaction.
511. the individual's self-understanding of what and where he or she is socially.
512. the individual's sense of self in a setting.
513. the individual's continuing sense of self.
514. the individuals' subjective interpretations of who they are, based on their sociodemographic characteristics, roles, personal attributes, and group memberships.
515. the instrumental use of emergent cultural symbols or, in other words, as a text that is read in relation to the cultural context of the organization.
516. the interaction between exploration of and commitment to a given cultural background.
517. the interface between the individual and the world, defining as it does what the individual will stand for and be recognized as.
518. the internal experience of gender, a fundamental sense of belonging to one sex or the other.
519. the internal history or memory by which Christians live individually and corporately.
520. the internalization of values and ideas integral to nursing.
521. the internalized positional designation linked to each role a person has in society.
522. the intersection between the individual and the collective.
523. the knowledge for an individual about paying an emotional attention on being a part of social group.
524. the language-based stereotype.
525. the linguistic construction of membership in one or more social groups or categories.
526. the manner in which teachers express their roles as teachers.
527. the meaning of self to itself or to another.
528. the meaning systems continuously created, adopted and personally adapted by individuals within socio-cultural contexts.
529. the meaning that individuals attach to themselves.
530. the meaning that various actors ascribe to themselves and the operation of which they are a part.
531. the meanings associated with the self, which can refer to personal attributes.
532. the meanings individuals attach to themselves in a particular role.
533. the meanings that individuals attach to themselves.
534. the meanings that people attach to themselves.
535. the meeting point, the point of suture, between on the one hand the discourses and practices which attempt to 'interpellate'.
536. the membership of an individual or a group of individuals in a political community.
537. the memories, experiences, relationships, and values that create one's sense of self.
538. the migrant's conception of self and feeling of belonging.
539. the narrative about the self.
540. the negation of the negation.

541. the neural pattern.
542. the notion that every object of our perception or person has basic property or essence.
543. the nurse's values and beliefs.
544. the objective reality that defines each place, person or entity, and which expresses its recognizable appearance.
545. the ongoing sense the self has of who it is, as conditioned through its ongoing interactions with others.
546. the opposite of Islamic socio-cultural features which are depicted rather negatively.
547. the organized set of characteristics an individual perceives as representing or defining the self in a given social situation.
548. the particular values, beliefs, and aspects of ourselves that we deem so important we consider them self-defining.
549. the pattern of meaning and value by which a person structures his or her life.
550. the percent of correctly labeled latent proteins and confusion as the percent of variables incorrectly associated to their latent proteins.
551. the perception of occupational interests, abilities, goals, and values, and the structure of the meanings that link these self-perceptions to career role.
552. the perception of the self in a situated context, but also as the perception of one's possible self in the future.
553. the persistence of self-consciousness across time.
554. the person we think we are and communicate to others.
555. the person we think we are.
556. the person's masculinity or femininity as determined by cultural and psychological qualities that are encouraged in one sex and discouraged in the other.
557. the perspective of the author (the observer, the analyst).
558. the portions of a self which are made up of the meanings that persons attach to the multiple roles they typically play in contemporary society.
559. the possibility of belonging to one or many groups.
560. the primitive notions of a calculus of individuals.
561. the process and result of self-determination of a person or group, the creation of an image of "I" and an image of "we".
562. the process of acquiring the values, attitudes, and skills of the single chosen profession.
563. the process of identification, of saying that this here is the same as that, or we are the same together, in this respect.
564. the process of interaction with others within a broad intergroup context.
565. the prominence of past military service, beliefs, and norms on an individual's post-military sense of self.
566. the properties an agent has and is thus used to describe how an agent defines itself.
567. the property of being one and the same.
568. the property of being recognizable as a particular kind of person in a given context.
569. the psychic representation of the self, which evolves over time through the individual's interaction with his/her interpersonal environment.

570. the psychological counterpoint to national identity.
571. the psychological manifestations of demographic categories.
572. the qualities, beliefs, etc., that make a particular person or group different from others.
573. the qualities, beliefs, etc. that make a particular person or group different from others.
574. the real self in comparison to the ideal self.
575. the recognition of membership in a given group and an affinity with other group members.
576. the reflexive venture through which an individual or a group strive to uphold a sensation of unity and continuity.
577. the relation established by psychological identification.
578. the relation of association determined by a claim to common membership in a social group whose boundaries are established through a process of ascription by group members and others.
579. the relationship a thing has to itself.
580. the relationship between a sentence's author and its grammatical subject.
581. the relationship between two or more related entities in a manner that asserts the sameness or equality.
582. the relatively persistent but always permeable formation of the self that provides a basic orientation for human agency in acting collectively and individually within a social-political world.
583. the representation and negotiation of social roles.
584. the result of a set of successive identifications transformed into a coherent and specific whole.
585. the result of affiliation to particular beliefs and possibilities which are available to them in their social context.
586. the right to be someone non-identical to state citizenship, and, at the same time, as a right to be united with someone else who is in the same position.
587. the right to be unique and different.
588. the role that they devise for themselves, based on social positions.
589. the sameness of a person or fact that a person or thing is itself and not something else.
590. the sameness of the individual that erases multiplicity and indeterminacy.
591. the self in moral space in which individuals more or less consciously situate themselves in the present, thereby to orient themselves to an ideal future.
592. the self in moral space.
593. the self-consciousness of an individual in the surrounding world.
594. the sense of belonging to a particular group or society.
595. the sense of belonging towards a particular group.
596. the sense of self as being male or female.
597. the set of characteristics and traits typical of successful people in specific settings.
598. the set of characteristics that allows a person to be known and identified within a group.
599. the set of characteristics that distinguishes a person, event, or entity among others sharing similar or different characteristics.

600. the set of meanings one holds for oneself as an occupant of a particular role.
601. the set of personal and behavioral features which define an individual as a member of a certain group based on race, ethnicity, religion, language, and culture of the people that differentiate themselves from other groups.
602. the set of qualities that make a person different from other people.
603. the set of qualities, beliefs, personality traits, appearance, and/or expressions that characterize a person or a group.
604. the social categories a person belongs to.
605. the social categories in which an individual claims membership, as well as the personal meaning associated with those categories.
606. the social constraints that frame traditional practices.
607. the social construction of a self, be it a state form, an institution or an individual, that makes action possible even as it limits the range of actions that are possible.
608. the social positioning of self and other.
609. the social representation of the sense of belonging to the nation-state institutions.
610. the socially determined answer to the question: "Who am I?"
611. the source of meaning and experience for people.
612. the stable, consistent, and reliable sense of who one is and what one stands for in the world.
613. the state of being exactly alike.
614. the state of being the same and not other.
615. the state of being the same as a person or thing described or claimed.
616. the state of having unique identifying characteristics held by no other person or thing.
617. the stories that one shares.
618. the stories that people tell about themselves and the image that they present to the world.
619. the story about the self.
620. the structure of the ego- an internal, self-creating, dynamic organization of needs, abilities, beliefs, and individual history.
621. the subject's fundamental or characteristic facial expression.
622. the subjective concept of oneself as a person.
623. the subjective knowledge, meanings, and experiences that are self-defining.
624. the sum of all the life experiences that a person has had from the very beginning of their life.
625. the sum of an individual's competence, emotions, autonomy, purpose, integrity and interpersonal relationships.
626. the system of relationships in which a person is involved.
627. the things that make one person or group of people different from others.
628. the triad of 'who others think I am', 'who I am' and 'who I want to be'.
629. the understanding of the self and of the others in relation to a context, a discipline, and a professional workplace.
630. the unifying concept encompassing terms like privacy, authentication, trust, rights, tracking, security, and other associated terms.
631. the unique set of social groups to which an actor belongs.
632. the unity of any object or subject.

633. the variations between motions of the same content that are caused by different skeleton sizes/proportions.
634. the various meanings attached to one-self and others, and in various social spaces through relationships implied by that identity.
635. the various meanings that outside observers typically associate with an organization.
636. the vast array of traits that describe us personally.
637. the way an individual chooses to identify him or herself, and identification as “the way others identify that individual.
638. the way an individual is recognized by themselves and others as a certain “kind of person”.
639. the way in which a person is, or wishes to be known by others.
640. the way in which a person sees him/herself—his/her “relation-to-self.”
641. the way in which persons change how they view self (mind, body, and spirit) in an effort to reconcile physical or body alterations.
642. the way in which students negotiate, construct, and perceive their roles in a given community of practice.
643. the way individuals give meaning to their existence in the world.
644. the way one defines oneself within social networks and in relation to others.
645. the way somebody considers their characteristics as a particular individual, especially in relation to the social environment they live or work in.
646. the way that individuals label themselves as members of particular groups.
647. the way we view ourselves in respect to specific contexts and groups.
648. the ways ‘in which the self is represented and understood in dynamic, multi-dimensional and evolving ways’.
649. the ways in which countries are depicted economically.
650. the ways in which he or she is similar to and different from other persons in body, conduct, and thought.
651. the ways in which individuals and collectivities are distinguished in their social relations with other individuals and collectivities.
652. the ways individuals describe themselves in a given context.
653. the ways we position and define ourselves within the narratives of the past.
654. the wholeness to be achieved at a stage in life.
655. the fact of being or feeling the same.
656. the fact of being, or feeling that you are, a particular type of person, organization, etc.
657. the individual characteristics by which a person or thing is recognized.
658. the qualities of a person or group which make them different from others.
659. the qualities that make a person, organization, etc. different from others.
660. the quality or condition of being a specific person or thing.
661. those habitual behaviors that give people their own distinctive styles of being in the world.
662. those narratives about individuals that are reifying, endorsable and significant.
663. those sustainable cross-spatiotemporal attributes of a brand which determine the brand’s essence from the perspective of the internal target group.
664. through a binary position: similarity and difference.
665. To know who I am is a species of knowing where I stand.

666. true God - relationship within existing communities but not necessarily between them.
667. undoubtedly fluid, not monolithic, most importantly multidimensional, and always in the process of becoming.
668. unique and non-reductive form, which is based on autonomy of consciousness and autobiographical narration.
669. unique traits and is constructed from the diversity of human beings and, at the same time, in relationships with other people.
670. values that individuals share with other individuals, and about what differentiates one set of individuals from another.
671. veterans' self-concept that derives from his/her military experience within a sociohistorical context.
672. ways in which students participate in communities of practice.
673. ways of talking about how learning changes who we are.
674. what is shared by a person.
675. what the organization represents for its consumers.
676. what we do and how we accomplish our tasks.
677. who a person is in relationship to others as well as to self.
678. who a person understands herself or himself to be in intersection with who others understand her or him to be.
679. who one is in the situation and notes the importance of discourse as a way of being a certain type of person.
680. who or what someone is, the various meanings someone can attach to oneself, or the meanings attributed to oneself by others.
681. who someone is or the name of a person.
682. who someone is.
683. who we are and with whom we 'belong' – in fact, language remains the main source for sustaining collective identity.
684. Who we are, where we're coming from?
685. who women are and how they identify themselves.
686. who you are in light of certain biological and social facts.